

On the estimation of country citation counts for European domestic research papers

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Abstract

A fairer measure of the influence and quality of a country's researchers will be the foreign citation score of its domestic papers, as that of its international papers will inevitably be affected by the capability of its partners and its overall citation scores will be greater for countries with many researchers. We hypothesised that this indicator would be strongly influenced by several independent factors. These are its propensity to have its papers co-authored internationally, the proportion of its research output classed as reviews (a measure of esteem), the percentage of its wealth that was devoted to research and development, and the percentage of foreign-born people among its population. We determined the correlation between the five-year mean foreign citation score of the domestic research papers of the 26 European members of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and these four parameters. It was possible to optimise the coefficients of these indicators so as to maximise this correlation at a high value ($r^2 = 0.90$). The resulting equation would therefore provide good estimates of the likely citation performance of individual countries from a knowledge of these parameters for a given year.

Introduction

The bibliometrics community has long been fascinated by counts of citations. Apart from a small but learned *oeuvre* on their temporal distribution (for example, Egghe, 2007; Golosovsky, 2021; Naheem et al, 2022), their main use has been to make comparisons between the quality of research, or at least the impact, of different entities. These may be the whole world, if different scientific fields are being compared, but more usually they are individual nations (Bonitz & Scharnhorst, 2001; Annalingam et al., 2014; Ho et al., 2018; Thelwall & Maflahi, 2020) or groups thereof (Onyancha, 2021), regions within them (Moskovkin et al., 2017; Eremenko, 2019), research institutions (Garcia-Zorita et al., 2009; Abbasi & Jamali, 2019), groups (Moed, 2010; Mryglod et al., 2013), and even individuals (Bornmann & Marx, 2014; Konar, 2021). However, there was little attempt to predict these scores, or to relate them to observable parameters, although Bonitz & Scharnhorst did evaluate national performance on the numbers of citations above or below those expected from the journals in which their papers were published.

On the other hand, there is also a body of literature on means to predict the citation scores of individual papers, or those of research groups. These can be based on numerous parameters, notably the impact factor of the journal in which the paper was published (Prathap et al., 2016; Abramo et al., 2017), the attention paid to the paper shortly after publication (Sathianathen et al., 2020), the numbers of Tweets that it attracted (Eysenbach, 2011; Peoples et al., 2016; Lumley et al., 2021), and other measures classed as Altmetrics (Finch et al., 2017).

Analyses of the research outputs of individual countries can be carried out in three ways. The first, and most obvious, way is to determine the mean citation count in a set time window of all the papers that contain one or more addresses within the target country. The second method takes account of the fractional contribution of the country to the paper, and credits it with that fraction of the citation count. For papers with no international collaboration, hereinafter

“domestic” papers, the fraction would be unity. This is a rather better measure of citation impact, particularly for small countries with much international co-authorship. The third method, which disregards all foreign contributions, is just to determine the citation score of domestic papers. We went one step further, and removed all citations from own country, as these are known to be biased towards papers from the country (Bakare & Lewison, 2017). The resulting score is usually much lower than the average for international papers, but it does give an unvarnished view of the citation performance of the country as viewed from abroad.

Methodology

We selected for our analysis the 26 European countries that have been Members of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). They include most, but not all, of the Member States of the European Union (EU) and in addition Iceland, Norway and Switzerland. They are listed in Table 1, with their populations in 2010 and their International Standards Organization digraph (ISO2) codes, which are used in Figure 1 for conciseness. The OECD publishes a wealth of statistical material about its Members, and we have extracted their expenditures on R&D as a percentage of their Gross Domestic Products (GDP) (E%), and the percentage of their populations that were born elsewhere (F%). From our analysis of their publications (articles and reviews only) in the Web of Science (WoS, © Clarivate Analytics) we also determined two additional parameters: the percentage of reviews (R%) as a mark of esteem (Lewison, 2009), and the percentage of their papers that were internationally co-authored (I%). The latter two indicators are rather different from the first two as they depend on research outputs and would be higher for countries whose research was well regarded by foreigners.

Table 1. List of 26 European countries that are Members of the OECD and whose research outputs were studied. Pop = population (millions) in 2015

<i>Country</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Pop</i>		<i>Country</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Pop</i>		<i>Country</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Pop</i>
Austria	AT	8.4		Hungary	HU	10.0		Poland	PL	38.2
Belgium	BE	10.8		Iceland	IS	0.32		Portugal	PT	10.6
Czechia	CZ	10.5		Ireland	IE	4.5		Slovakia	SK	5.4
Denmark	DK	5.5		Italy	IT	60.3		Slovenia	SI	2.0
Estonia	EE	1.3		Latvia	LV	2.2		Spain	ES	46.0
Finland	FI	5.4		Lithuania	LT	3.3		Sweden	SE	9.3
France	FR	64.4		Luxembourg	LU	0.5		Switzerland	CH	7.8
Germany	DE	78.7		Netherlands	NL	16.6		UK	UK	64.7
Greece	GR	11.3		Norway	NO	4.9				

For our first analysis, we interrogated the WoS for publication year 2015, and determined the numbers of papers for each of the 26 countries, the numbers of reviews, and the numbers of domestic papers, which had no address outwith the selected country. [They would have excluded papers where an author had addresses in multiple countries.] We then determined the numbers of citations to these domestic papers for the five years, 2015 to 2019, by subtracting the numbers in the four years 2020-23 from the total number of “Citing Articles”, and then also subtracting the number of citations from papers with an address in the country.

For some countries, the number of domestic papers was greater than 10,000, which is the limit for the WoS citation analysis procedure. For these countries, we divided up their domestic papers by the initial letter of the journals in which they were published into groups so that each group had fewer than 10,000 papers. For example, for France with 33,749 domestic papers, we divided them into four groups: A* to D*; E* to I*; J* to O*; and others. The mean citation score was denoted Actual Citation Impact, ACI.

We then created a spreadsheet with four columns for the independent parameters, with E% and F% taken from the year 2010 as we estimated that it would take up to five years from the arrival of a researcher from abroad, or the allocation of money for research, to show up in the form of published papers. We created a composite independent variable by multiplying each of the four parameters for each country by a coefficient, and adding them together. We then determined the correlation between this composite indicator (CI) and the mean foreign citations per domestic paper, and adjusted each of the coefficients so as to maximize the correlation. After several iterations it was not possible to increase it further, and we then could write an equation that best correlated the CI with the ACI values. We then plotted ACI for each country against CI, and selected the best-fitting trend-line, which turned out to be an exponential fit. We then computed the expected values of ACI for each country, which could be compared with the observed values.

This exercise was then repeated for 2010 publications with values of E% and F% for 2005.

Results

The 26 European countries vary greatly in size, from Germany, with almost 79 million inhabitants in 2015, to Iceland, with barely 0.3 million, and with corresponding differences in research output. For 2015, we were able to develop four coefficients that maximised the correlation between CI and the value of ACI for foreign citations to domestic papers, which for a linear relationship gave $r^2 = 0.905$. The equation was:

$$CI(2015) = 0.45 \times F\% + 15.5 \times E\% + 12 \times R\% + 0.8 \times I\%$$

A partial spreadsheet, with the top and bottom performing three countries is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Partial spreadsheet for six European countries in 2015

<i>Country</i>	<i>Factor</i>	<i>Switzerland</i>	<i>Denmark</i>	<i>Ireland</i>	<i>Estonia</i>	<i>Hungary</i>	<i>Latvia</i>
GDP 2010		641.9	283.9	209.5	19.4	113.1	23.0
Foreign 2010 %	0.45	26.1	7.5	16.7	16.4	4.1	14.8
R&D 2010 %	15.5	2.7	2.9	1.6	1.6	1.1	0.6
Papers 2015		31559	19583	8902	2025	7662	919
Reviews		2299	1306	853	69	387	29
Reviews %	12	7.3	6.7	9.6	3.4	5.1	3.2
Domestic papers		9196	7221	3446	766	3393	426
Internat'l ones%	0.8	70.9	63.1	61.3	62.2	55.7	53.6
All foreign cites		610444	356115	144904	44017	87632	9434
All foreign CPP		19.3	18.2	16.3	21.7	11.4	10.3
Dom. foreign cites		108075	69997	33372	3902	14227	1441
Dom. foreign CPP		11.8	9.7	9.7	5.1	4.2	3.4

Estimated value		11.3	9.1	11.1	4.7	4.8	3.5
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When the values of ACI were plotted against CI, determined by this equation, the best least-squares trend-line was not linear, but exponential, see Figure 1. The equation for the trend-line was:

$$ACI = 1.158 \times \exp(0.0115 \times CI)$$

and the correlation coefficient, r^2 , increased to 0.934. This is not perfect, and the spots for some countries lie well above the trend-line, and others lie well below. The average departure was 8%.

When we repeated the exercise for the 2010 papers, the best-fit equation on the assumption of a linear relationship was similar, but the coefficients were slightly changed:

$$CI(2010) = 0.2 \times F\% + 16 \times E\% + 11 \times R\% + 0.6 \times I\%$$

The correlation coefficient, r^2 , equaled 0.838, but when the individual country spots were plotted against CI, the best fit turned out to be a power-law trend-line, with its equation given by:

$$ACI = 0.0017 \times CI^{1.708}$$

and an r^2 value of 0.859. The average difference between the calculated and observed values of ACI increased to 14%.

We note in passing that the average value of ACI increased from 7.16 in 2010 to 7.55 in 2015, but the increase was quite small (5.4%). The overall rate of internationalism went up from 51.2% to 55.5%, or by 8.4%, and this is likely to have led to a larger increase in the citation score of the whole set of papers (i.e., including international ones) from each country.

Discussion and conclusions

This was a preliminary exercise to see if the citation counts of individual countries could be forecasted from other parameters, including those of its papers. Of course, the sheer quality of its researchers must be a major factor, and this is probably responsible for much of the departure from the trend-lines seen in Figure 1. Thus the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal and Spain seem to do consistently better than their intrinsic parameters suggested, and Austria and Slovakia less well. Another important factor may be the extent to which research in a country depends on contestable grants. In principle, this could be discerned from the acknowledgements on its research papers, although this is a major task. A third factor could be the resources devoted to research, which must depend greatly on its wealth. However, although Norway (from the above list of high performers) is very wealthy, Portugal is not, although it is clearly making an increasing effort to transform itself into a research-intensive country, with its R&D expenditures rising from less than 0.3% of GDP in the early 1980s to more than 1.6% in 2020, and this policy change may be attracting able people into research. It has also attracted a large number of female researchers, and their participation rate in cancer research, for example, was easily the highest in Europe between 2009 and 2019 (Lewison et al., 2022).

In subsequent work, we plan to investigate whether another factor may be the subject mix in the countries' research portfolios, as some fields tend to receive more citations than others, and this could be a fifth factor in causing some countries to perform above or below expectations. Although most of the papers in the WoS are in English, some countries continue to publish papers in their national language, which tend to attract fewer citations. This could be another

factor that influences their overall citation performance. Our objective remains how to show what steps a country can take in order to improve its citation score and, arguably also, the impact and utility of its research.

Figure 1. Plot of mean ACI for foreign citations of domestic research papers from 26 European countries in 2015, and least-squares trend-line. For ISO2 codes, see Table 1

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